

A Review Article on Ayurvedic Management of Urdhwaga Amlapitta

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Abstract :- Amlapitta is one of the most common disease in the all-age groups and in all classes and community. Amlapitta is Pitta predominance disease which is related to Annavaahasrotas occurs due to Mandagni and Ama. When Amla Guna of pachakPitta increases is called Amlapitta. Pitta Vardhak Ahar Vihar, irregular and improper food habits, busy stressful lifestyle, hurry, worry, anxiety etc are the main causes of prevalence of disease i.e. Amlapitta. Acharya Charak has not mentioned Amlapitta as a separate disease but described in Grahni as one of its lakshan. Ayurvedic science helps for removing root cause of disease with the help of various Shaman, Shodhan and Pathyapathya. Nowadays due to unawareness about Prakriti people are practicing inappropriate diet and lifestyle which leads to disturbances in digestive system. Due to this pitta is imbalanced or takes an upward movement, then it is called urdhwagaamlapitta. In Amashaya when KledakKapha is increased, Pitta becomes diluted and Dushit causes Daha and Ushma in Amashaya. The cardinal features of amlapitta are Avipaka (indigestion), Tikta-amlodgara (sore and bitter belching), Hritkanthadaha (heart and throat burn).

Keywords:- Amlapitta, Pitta, Agni, Agnimandhya, Annavaahasrotas.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Srotas or channels which carry 'Anna' or food are called Annavaahasrotas. This can be correlated to the alimentary tract or gastrointestinal tract or digestive tract. Disturbance in the physiological co-ordination between these will be manifested as disease. According to Acharya Charaka, the Annavaahasrotas are 2 in number. They are rooted in – Aamashya and vamaparshva. (cha.vi.5/7). In ayurveda, it is believed that Agnimandya (indigestion of food) is the main root cause of all the disease^[1]. The major reason behind Agnimandya is intake of faulty dietary habits. Due to the present lifestyle and unawareness of one's prakriti. Digestive disorder which are very common in all age group. In Ayurveda, pitta is of two types as Adhoga and Urdhwaga Amlapitta. When pitta takes an upward course i.e., vomiting, headache, burning sensation, loss of appetite then it is called Urdhwaga Amlapitta. It includes different symptoms like Aruchi, Gaurav, Gurukoshthatva, Shiroruja, Utklesh, Tiktamudgar^[2]. Urdhwagaamlapitta is caused by mainly intake of aharas which is not suited to one's prakriti. Amla, Katu, Lavana, Guru, Snigdha, Abhishandhi Ahara^[3]. When pitta takes a downward course then, it is called Adhoga Amlapitta.

II. HISTORICAL REVIEW

- Kashyap Samhita – In Kashyap Samhita Amlapitta has been mentioned as a separate entity in chapter 16th of Khilasthana.^[4]
- Madhava Nidana – after Kashyap Madhava Nidana is the 2nd text which gives importance to Amlapitta and describes its aetiopathogenesis and symptomatology in details.^[5]

III. TYPES OF AMLAPITTA

- According to Dosha Dushti

Kashyap samhita	Madhava nidana
1. Vataja Amlapitta	1. Vataadhikya Amlapitta
2. Pittaja Amlapitta	2. Kaphaadhikya Amlapitta
3. Kaphaja Amlapitta	3. Vata-kaphaadhikya Amlapitta
	4. Shleshma – pittajaadhikya Amlapitta

Table 1: Dosha Dushti

• According to SthanaDushti^[6,7]

Urdhwaga Amlapitta	Vamana- (Harita,Pitta,Neela,Krishna,Rakta,Raktabha,MansodhakabhaVarna,Atiamla,Atipicchila,Accha,Shleshmamyata,Vividharasa,Amlodgara,Tiktodgara), Kanthahrid, kukshi Daha, Shirashoola, Kapha- Pittaja, Jawra, Kandu, Mandala, Pidaka
Adhoga Amlapitta	Trishna, Daha, Murchha, Moha, Hrillasa, Kotha, Agnimandya, Harsha, Sweda, Angapittata

Table 2: Sthana Dushti

IV. CAUSES OF AMLAPITTA- ACCORDING TO KASHYAP^[8]

- **AharajNidana**–Viruddhaahara(incompatible foods),Adhyasana (eating too soon after a meal), Amabhojana (undigested food), Bhojana taken in Ajeerna(indigestion), Gurubhojana (heavyfood), Snigdha(over intake of oily things), Atirukshanna(over intake of dry things), Abhishyandibhojana(food that causes hyperserection)
- **ViharajNidana**- Ratrijagarana (awakeovernighttime), Dhatukshaya (debility of tissues), Upavasa(fasting),

Divaswapna (sleeping over day time), Vegadharana(with holding urges)

• **Samanyalakshan**-^[9]

- Avipaka(indigestionof food)
- Tkitaudgar(pungent and sour belching)
- Klama(lassitude)
- Utklesh(nausea)
- Gaurav (heaviness)
- Hriddah(burning sensation in epigastric region)
- Kanthdah(tympanitis)
- Aruchi(anorexia)

V. SAMPRAPTI– (K.S. 16/10-12)

Excessive consumption of Amla,Tikta,Katu,UshnaAhara

• **Sampraptighatakas**

- Dosh – Tridosha(mainly pitta)
- Dushya – Rasa,Rakta
- Srotas – Annavaha
- Agni- Jatharagni
- Ama- Jatharagnimandhyajanya
- Udbhavasthana- Amashaya
- Adhisthana- Adhoamashaya
- Sancharana- Annavaha
- Swabhava- Chirakari
- Pradhanta- Pitta dosha pradhana

• **Purvarupa:**

In ancient ayurvedic texts, no specific purvarupa are given for amlapitta.

• **Investigation –**

- Gastroscopy (upper gastro intestinal endoscopy)
- Oesophageal phmonitering
- Barium meal x-ray
- Serology and histology for H. Pylori

• **Management of Amlapitta**-^[10]

- According to Acharya Yogaratnakar and Acharya Kashyap
- Shodhanchikitsa
 - ✓ Vamana – is the 1 st line of treatment for Amlapitta
 - ✓ Virechana- after that mruduvirechana is indicated for Amlapitta.
 - ✓ Basti – AsthapanaBasti should be administered in chronic Amlapitta.
 - Shaman chikitsa
 - Shodhanachikitsa is followed by shaman chikitsa.

- **Rasa /Bhasma / Pishti –**
 - Sootasekhar Rasa
 - Kamadudha Rasa
 - Shankhbhasma
 - Pravalpishti
- **Churna–**
 - Avipattikarchurna
 - Triphalachurna
 - Satavarichurna
 - Panchnimadichurna
 - Mulethichurna

- **Vati-**
 - Sobhagyashunthimodak

- **Kwath-**
 - Patoladikwath
 - Bhunimadikwath
 - Panchtikwath

- **Ghrit –**
 - Vasaghrit
 - Satavarighrit
 - Drakshaghrit

- **Single Drugs used in Amlapitta^[11]**

Ativisha, Bhringaraja, Guduchi, Kapardabhasma, Patola, Satavari, Suktibhasma, pishti, Shankhabhasma, Mukta pishti, Pravalabhasma.

	Pathya	Apathya
Ahara	Purana shali, Mudga, Goghrita, Godugdha, Jangala Mamsa, Patola, Vastuka, Dadima, Amalaka, madhu, Karela, Nimba	Amla, Lavana, Katu, Vidahi, Guru, Tila, Kulatha, Madya, Kanji,
Vihara	Sitopchara, Vishrama, sheetaljal,	Atapasevana, Vega dharana, Krodha, Shoka, Chinta, Bhram, Divaswapna.

Table 3: Pathya and Apathya for Amlapitta^[12]

VI. COMPLICATIONS

The complication of Amlapittais: Jwara, Atisara, Pandu, Shula, Shotha, Aruchi, Bhrama, the following complications causes dhatushaya does not get cure.^[13]

VII. CONCLUSION

As a review, all the material taken through classical Ayurvedic text, Kashyap Samhita, MadhavNidana, Charakas well as modern aspects. Intake of proper food and behaviour to avoid the Amlapitta. Everybody should obey the rules of intake of food.

Mainly excess intake of Nidana of Amlapittashould be avoided as well as GIT (gastrointestinal tract) and Jatharagni should be maintained naturally as season, Prakruti etc that are prescribed by text. Excess of salt, sour, spicy food, irregular intake of food, alcohol, tea, caffeine as well as NSAID, steroid, Mansik Vikar which are mentioned in CharakViman 4 are most commonest causative factor of Amlapitta.

All person's with acidity can take milk diet. Yet milk is excellent in the condition especially when preceded by fast, adjusted to your general condition. For a time, it is better to use foods requiring only moderate mastication of the food, since mastication naturally increases the flow of gastric juice with its acid. Yet insufficient mastication of the food chosen will aggravate by causing gastric irritation. It is very important not to over eat food, but to take small meals, three times a day.

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